

Legal Literacy a Missing Link in Education: Evaluation of New Education Policy in The Context of Viksit Bharat

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Abstract:

Education plays a pivotal role in socio-economic advancement, and in shaping a just society based on democratic principles. Educational policies thus play a crucial role in altering the ethos of the nation. The National Education Policy (NEP), 2020 is one such attempt to transform India's education system through multidisciplinary approach, holistic education and value-based pedagogy. While inclusivity, and implementation challenges of the policy have been thoroughly evaluated in the existing scholarship, many conceptual gaps in the policy and their implications on overall development of the nation remain inadequately explored. Given this, the study focuses on legal literacy as a conceptual gap in the policy. By employing doctrinal methodology, this paper investigates whether NEP has structurally incorporated legal literacy in its provisions as well as the objectives. The analysis indicates the insufficient focus on legal literacy illustrating a conceptual gap between the policy's multidisciplinary and holistic approach. The paper argues this omission may restrict accomplishment of developmental goals allied to the objectives of Viksit Bharat, 2047. It concludes by emphasizing the need of incorporating legal literacy in higher education to strengthen democracy as envisioned in the objectives of Viksit Bharat.

Keywords - National Education Policy, Legal Literacy, Multidisciplinary approach, Viksit Bharat

Introduction:

Education has been instrumental in shaping the social fabric. Beyond imparting knowledge, it is an apparatus to bring social change and strengthen democracy by nurturing responsible and aware citizens. Globally as every nation is striving to attain sustainable development, this role of education has become far more crucial. Given this, the New Education Policy, 2020 is set to alter curriculum design, pedagogy and institutional structure that is aligned with the needs of the rapidly evolving modern world; as education is expected to foster not just skilled individuals but also responsible and aware citizens. The objectives of viksit Bharat further reinforces this vision by focusing on inclusive and participatory governance.

To bring such revolutionary change, inclusion of legal literacy in mainstream education has become one of the essential competencies. Even though legally there have been many

remedial mandates to enhance legal awareness of citizens; its incorporation in formal education will definitely shape civic competence and social consciousness thereby bringing structural change. The indicators of rule of law index also highlight the pressing demand of it. Even though in the year 2025, India has performed relatively better in overall ranking of the index by standing 86th out of 143 countries, its relatively lower rankings in civil justice and fundamental rights that is 114 and 103 respectively out of 143 countries indicate a need for structural change (WJP Rule of Law Index, n.d.). Hence, integrating legal literacy in higher education will help in attaining the policy vision of both NEP and Viksit Bharat in reality. So, this paper particularly analyzes integration of legal literacy in NEP and its consequences on the developmental goals envisioned by Viksit Bharat, 2047.

Hereafter the paper is divided into four parts. Firstly it has outlined the objectives and methodology of the research. Subsequently, it explains the meaning and significance of legal literacy along with contextualizing it in NEP and Viksit Bharat. Lastly it concludes by highlighting the significance of legal literacy to foster empowerment of individuals, ultimately to strengthen democracy as outlined in the developmental goals envisioned in Viksit Bharat, 2047 agenda.

Objectives:

- To define legal literacy within the educational and constitutional framework.
- To analyze the gaps regarding legal literacy in the framework of New Education Policy, 2020.
- To assess the impact of inclusion or omission of legal literacy in NEP on the vision of Viksit Bharat

Methodology:

This study has employed a qualitative and doctrinal methodology to examine whether the NEP adequately incorporates legal literacy as a core component of educational reform and its implications on accomplishing developmental goals as envisioned in Viksit Bharat 2047. Consequently, the research has used thematic content analysis of policy texts, constitutional provisions, and scholarly articles to identify the inclusion of legal literacy in the educational objectives and curriculum design.

Data Analysis and Findings:

Legal Literacy: Meaning, significance and Government Initiatives

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) defines legal literacy as “the awareness of primary level legal rights and obligations within a legal system, and the tools to enforce them” (Bhardwaj, 2025). Simply put, legal literacy is not confined to being informed of the existence of the law. As stated by Singh, (2025) legal literacy involves knowledge of legal rights, legal processes along with the application of legal rights. Legal literacy not only instills awareness among people to deal with situations when they are immediately affected by any illegal act but is a prerequisite for all individuals to lead a dignified life. Even so, persistent foundational illiteracy, complex and technical legal language, and lack of competency in English language have been major hurdles keeping citizens away from effectively engaging with the judicial system (Raza, 2021).

Amidst this, many remedial efforts were taken by the Government of India. The notable inclusion of Article 39A under the 42nd Amendment Act, 1976 as a part of the Directive Principles of State Policy has mandated free legal aid particularly to the marginalized sections of the society. Subsequently, with the enactment of the Legal Services Authority Act, 1987 statutory apex body National Legal Service Authority (NALSA), along with decentralized bodies at state and district level namely; State Legal Service Authority (SLSA) and District Legal Service Authority (DLSA) were established ultimately facilitating the legal aid services and legal awareness programs in the country (Singh, 2025). Under these bodies many workshops, seminars, legal aid camps, awareness programs along with Lok Adalats are conducted to enhance the legal awareness among people. While these judicial actions have been actively working on enhancing legal awareness, integrating legal literacy in formal education has become significantly important to bring structural transformation.

New Education Policy and Legal Literacy:

Succeeding the educational reform of 1986; NEP, 2020 has a prime aim to reform the educational system of India aligning with the needs of the rapidly changing modern world. With the prime aim of making India a global power, this policy has prioritized inclusive education, multidisciplinary and holistic approach to enhance critical thinking as well as holistic development of individuals. The policy has also foreseen the role of education to cultivate responsible citizens to strengthen democracy and rule of law. Considering this, incorporation of legal literacy as a part of the curriculum becomes essential. This section therefore, critically

analyzes the way in which legal literacy has been incorporated in NEP, particularly in higher education.

As enlisted in the fundamental objectives of the policy curriculum is to be inclusive of democratic principles, humanitarian as well as constitutional values. As stated in the policy, higher education is to be transformed by establishing higher education institutions (HEI), marked by flexibility and multidisciplinary approach. So, there are no rigid boundaries between different streams or disciplines. These particular aspects of the policy have been widely praised as it has integrated disciplines across arts, sciences, humanities along with vocational subjects and has allowed students to pursue courses from different fields. Whilst inclusion of legal disciplines could have been a foundational step to streamline legal literacy in mainstream education, law being a professional course requiring specific skillset, trained practice and having a distinct regulatory body i.e. bar council of India; has not been included under this multidisciplinary approach of the policy. As discussed earlier, even though there has been explicit mention of ideas of justice, equality, liberty, fraternity, secularism, pluralism and humanitarian values to be imparted through education; it seems to be covered through civics education, ethics, and political science courses. Where these courses do build legal awareness but they are insufficient to bring about legal literacy as they do not adequately address the practical legal knowledge. i.e. legal procedures, rights enforcement, etc.

Overall, the policy strongly advocates legal awareness but fails to structurally incorporate legal literacy as a part of curriculum.

Contextualizing Legal Literacy and Viksit Bharat:

Viksit Bharat 2047, is an agenda put forward by the Government of India to revamp India, that is, Bharat into a developed nation by 2047. It has a principle aim to make India a self reliant nation by attaining holistic development through socio-economic and political transformation. Accordingly, it has focused on substantive GDP, digital empowerment, social inclusion, education and skill development, accessible healthcare, infrastructural growth, sustainable development along with enhanced citizen participation and governance.

Amidst this, the role of education becomes pivotal because of its ability to socialize people, enhance critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. Quality education will not only bring about economic growth but substantive social growth. In such a scenario, inclusion of legal literacy in formal education becomes significant; without which individuals would not be able to

claim their rights, challenge violations or even seek remedies. Furthermore, overseeing the role of legal literacy will disproportionately affect marginalized sections of the society ultimately impeding sustainable development, effective governance as well as citizen participation.

Conclusion:

This paper, by employing doctrinal and qualitative methodology, has contextualized legal literacy in New Education Policy, 2020 as well as in Viksit Bharat by considering it as one of the essential competencies required for social transformation and nation building. The findings indicate that, even though NEP is set to revolutionize the education system aligned with the needs of contemporary times, it has inadequately focused on legal literacy which will directly hamper the rule of law, democratic spirit, sustainable development and a just governance. As the spirit of true democracy lies in people who are aware, responsible, who do not just exercise their rights but hold the system accountable thereby enhancing governance and public participation for which legal empowerment has become vital. So, amidst such major educational and visionary socio-economic and political reforms, legal knowledge should not be an ivory tower as it will only reproduce the existing inequalities. Hence it is a dire necessity that legal literacy should not be confined to constitutional remedies or only to legal profession, rather it should be structurally embedded in mainstream education to bring about the vision of Viksit Bharat into reality and transform the nation.

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